

Fluphenazine increases cis-platin efficacy in colon cancer cells

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Abstract

Background: In Western nations, colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common and currently one of the deadliest malignancies. Cisplatin is a medication that is commonly used to treat colon cancer. Moreover, in a recent study, fluphenazine (FPZ), an antipsychotic medicine, was discovered to be an anticancer agent against colon cancer cells. the goal of this investigation was to see if cisplatin coupled with FPZ had any synergistic apoptotic effects on HCT116.

Method: On colon cancer cell lines HCT116, the cytotoxic activity of FPZ in conjunction with cis-platin was tested. Furthermore, using qPCR and western blot, accordingly, the protein concentrations of BAX and BCL-2, in addition to their gene expression levels, were evaluated.

Result: In an MTT assay, cisplatin in conjunction with FPZ significantly reduced the activity of HCT116 human colon cancer cells as compared to one of the medicines given alone. Reduced and enhanced expression levels of the bcl-2 (ID: 596) and bax (Gene ID: 581) genes and proteins, respectively, confirmed this finding.

Conclusion: Our data imply that using FPZ as a synergistic drug with cisplatin could be a highly effective technique to increase apoptosis and achieve anticancer synergism. As a result, FPZ could be a promising alternative to cisplatin-based colon cancer therapy.

Keywords: apoptosis, colon cancer, fluphenazine, cisplatin, synergistic effect, bax, bcl-2.

1. Introduction

The third most common malignancy, colorectal cancer (CRC), is the second leading contributor to cancer-associated causes of death. Globally, responsible for 11% of all confirmed cases of cancer (1-4).

Cisplatin is a widely used chemotherapeutic drug additionally referred to cisplatinum or cis-diamminedichloroplatinum (II). It has been applied to treat a range of human malignancies, including bladder, head and neck, and colorectal cancer (5, 6).

Nevertheless, cisplatin's efficacy in the therapy of colorectal cancer (CRC) is limited, with less than 20% of patients achieving a clinical response using it alone (7, 8). As a result, the emergence of new cancer therapies is critical, but the process is slow, expensive, and has a poor approval rate. in order to solve the difficulties associated with the production of new drugs for cancer therapy, it is critical to develop and test novel pharmaceutical techniques (9, 10).

Drug repurposing, also termed as medicine repositioning, is the process of transferring an existing drug's characteristics from one

therapeutic area to another. Based on past drug clinical trial findings and toxicological testing, drug repurposing may result in cheaper total development expenses and shorter development schedules, which are essential for clinical application (11).

Antipsychotic medications have a lengthy history of clinical usage and tolerable safety, making them ideal candidates for therapeutic repurposing. Antipsychotic medicines, which have been used for decades to treat a wide range of psychiatric disorders, are now being reported to have significant anti-cancer capabilities against a wide range of cancers (12).

Fluphenazine (FPZ) is a neuroleptic and antidepressant medicine that is commonly used in psychotherapy to heal psychotic patients suffering from several of mental illnesses, such as schizophrenia, mania, extreme anxiety, and aberrant behavior (13). In a significant study, Xu et al. discovered that FPZ reduced the lifespan of metastatic triple negative breast cancer cells (TNBC). In vitro, it increased mitochondria-mediated intrinsic apoptosis and triggered G0/G1 cell cycle arrest.

Furthermore, FPZ significantly reduced the migration and invasion of metastatic TNBC cells. They believe that FPZ might be used in anti-cancer clinical studies as an FDA-approved medication (14). Moreover, S. Klutznny et al. indicate that FPZ results in cell deaths by hypoxia in HCT116 tumor spheroid cultivated in low oxygen environments by triggering an overactive hypoxia stress reaction and doing so through the stress-response transcription factor (ATF4) (15, 16). In this way, the goal of this experimental study is to see if FPZ and cisplatin can work together to increase apoptosis in colon cancer cells or not. Therefore, the goal of this experimental study is to see if FPZ and cisplatin can work together to increase apoptosis in colon cancer cells or not.

2. Method

Cell culture and drug treatment: The HCT116 colorectal cancer cell line was bought from Iran's Pasteur Institute. In Dulbecco's Modified Eagles Medium (DMEM; Bioidea, Iran) fortified with 10% fetal bovine serum, streptomycin (100 g/mL), and penicillin (100 U/mL), cells were cultured at 37°C in a humid incubator with 5% CO₂.

Cell viability assay: The rate of tumor cell growth inhibition was assessed using the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide test (MTT; Sigma Chemical Co., St. Louis, MO). 96-well plates at a density of 1×10^4 cells per well were used to implant colon cancer cell lines, which were then given 24 hours to adhere before receiving treatment.

After 48 hours of cisplatin (0-48 M) treatment, either by itself or alongside with FPZ (0-100 M), the cell media was removed, and 100 L/well of MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL in PBS) was applied to all well according to the MTT protocol. Three hours were spent incubating the cells in the dark. The MTT solution was extracted after this time interval, and the formazan crystals were solubilized using DMSO (100 L/well). A negative control of 0.5 percent DMSO (0 mg/ml) was employed. Epoch Microplate Spectrophotometer was used to detect absorbance at 570 nm (Biotek, USA).

Cell survivability = absorption of sample - absorption of control (negative) / (positive) The inhibition rate (%) is calculated as $(1 - \text{experiment group's absorbance/control group's absorbance})$.

Analysis of the joint effects of cisplatin and FPZ: Using the ComboSyn software (ComboSyn Inc.), a combination index (CI) was established to determine if the effects of the two drugs were supplementary, opposing, or interdependent. Chou devised a method for medication mixtures and general dose-effect analysis (Paramus, NJ, USA). The impact of the combination treatment was classified as synergistic if CI was lower than 1, additive if CI=1, or antagonistic if CI>1 (9).

Quantitative Real-time PCR (qRT-PCR): The level of gene expression profiles of apoptotic cells were examined using qRT-PCR. Following the manufacturer's procedure, RNA samples were extracted using TRIZOL reagent (Invitrogen, USA) and DNase-treated with a DNA-free kit (Ambion, USA). Following the manufacturer's directions, 700 ng of RNA was used to create first-strand cDNA using the High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, UK). The Rotor Gene 6000 was used to execute the real-time PCR reaction (Corbett, Concorde, NSW, Australia). A negative control was also employed for replication reliability, in which all of the elements of the reaction were included in the microtube apart from the cDNA. Lastly, the relative number of RNAs was determined using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C}$ (livac) (fold change) approach.

Western blot: Total cell protein extracts were generated in accordance with manufacturer's instructions, and they were subsequently separated using SDS-PAGE and 10% gel. Proteins were then added to a PVDF membrane (polyvinylidene difluoride). Primary antibodies were incubated overnight on membrane. The membranes in question were subsequently treated with HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies for 1 hour at room temperature. The ECLPlus reagent was used to visualize immunoreactive bands (Millipore, Billerica, MA). In the Western blot study, GAPDH was used as a loading control.

Statistical analysis: Graphpad Prism7 was used for data analysis. The data is explained utilizing the mean and standard error mean. For evaluating the means of more than two categories, a one-way ANOVA was employed. To ensure reproducibility, all experiments were repeated three times. Variations were considered statistically significant at p-values of 0.05.

3. Result

Synergistic cytotoxic Effect of FPZ and cisplatin in human colon cancer: At first An MTT test was used to detect single drug-induced inhibition of growth. For cisplatin, the concentrations were 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, and 48 M, whereas for FPZ, the concentrations were 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 50, and 100 M. An MTT test was carried 48 hours after treatment. Both cisplatin and FPZ had dose-dependent effects, as can be seen in Fig. 1. Employing GraphPad Prism software, the IC₅₀ values of cisplatin and FPZ in the HCT116 colon cancer cell line reported as 17.49 μ M ($r=0.99$) and 31.64 μ M ($r=0.99$).

The median-effect approach of Chou was used to identify whether the two medications had synergistic, antagonistic, or additive

effects based on the two-drug mixture in constant ratio. Combination treatment was considerably more cytotoxic than either medication alone ($p < 0.05$), as demonstrated in Fig. 2B. Moreover, the median-effect technique revealed that the values of

combination index (CI) were < 1 for all dose-effect curves of single or combined medication therapy, except for the combination of $10 \mu\text{M}$ FPZ with $3 \mu\text{M}$ cisplatin (Fig. 1A, Table I), showing that the two treatments operated synergistically.

Figure 1: After treatment with different doses of cisplatin, fluphenazine, and a combination of them, HCT116 cell survival was measured as a percentage.

Figure 2: FPZ, cisplatin, and their mixture have a growth inhibitory effect on human colon cancer cells. Following 48 hours of treatment with different concentration of fluphenazine alone, cisplatin alone, or their mix, growth inhibition was measured. A mean standard deviation is used to represent the data.

Figure 3: The median-effect approach of Ting-Chao Chou revealed a synergistic cytotoxic effect of fluphenazine and cisplatin in the human colon cancer cell line HCT116. The median-effect approach was used to assess the dose-effect curves

of solo or mixed drug treatment. The readings of the combination index (CI) were < 1 , showing that the two treatments worked together synergistically. CDDP, cisplatin; FPZ, fluphenazine; CF, cisplatin+fluphenazine.

Table 1: Cisplatin CI values in combination with fluphenazine in HCT116 cells at various dosages

Cisplatin (μM)	Fluphenazine (μM)	Fa	CI value
3	10	0.16	1.16
6	15	0.32	0.99
9	20	0.43	0.98
12	25	0.52	0.97
15	30	0.59	0.96
18	35	0.66	0.92
21	40	0.75	0.78
24	50	0.83	0.67
48	100	0.95	0.52

FPZ Enhanced Cisplatin-Induced Apoptosis: We then used Real-time PCR and western blot analysis to see if FPZ could increase cisplatin-induced apoptosis. The RT-qPCR data are shown in Figure 4. In comparison to the control group, cisplatin alone reduced *bcl-2* mRNA expression while increasing *bax* mRNA expression. The combined group exhibited a much lower level of

bcl-2 than the cisplatin group, but a considerably higher level of *bax*. Along with real-time PCR, we also looked at *bax* and *bcl-2* protein expression. The results of the Western blot and statistical analysis of the proteins BCL-2 and BAX confirmed the mRNA results for these two genes.

Figure 4: Cisplatin and FPZ had different effects on the expression of *bcl-2* and *bax* mRNA. mRNA levels of (A) *bax* and (B) *bcl-2*. When compared to the cisplatin groups, the combination group showed significantly reduced *bcl-2* mRNA levels, but considerably greater *bax* mRNA levels.

Figure 5: protein expression patterns of BCL-2, BAX, and GAPDH in HCT116.

4. Discussion

We discovered that combining FPZ and cisplatin suppressed HCT116 colon cancer proliferation by inducing cell death in human HCT116 cancerous colon cells. Because of its inhibition, FPZ combined with cisplatin seems to be a viable and successful target therapy against CRC.

Cancer research necessitates the development of innovative therapeutic techniques with low side effects and high efficacy. A well-known anticancer medication known as cisplatin is widely utilized for treating a number of cancers, such as testicular, head and neck, ovarian, cervical, non-small cell lung, and gastric carcinoma. Cisplatin's cytotoxic activity is largely due to its reaction with inter- and intra-strand DNA, which results in the

production of covalent cisplatin-DNA adducts. Intrinsic or acquired tumor cell resistance generally limits the clinical therapeutic benefit of cisplatin. Furthermore, cisplatin's nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity, particularly at larger dosages, have hampered the treatment's success (17, 18). Combination therapy has long been known to diminish cell viability and clonogenic development while also lowering toxicity in cancer patients. In terms of biological function, phenothiazines are a diverse group of compounds. The amphipathic nature of phenothiazines causes them to interact with biological membranes. Depending on the pH of the surroundings, the thiazine nucleus can be hydrophilic or even positively charged, whereas the side chain can be hydrophilic or even positively charged (19, 20). In a study published in 2019, Carmo discovered that phenothiazines, such as trifluoperazine and fluphenazine, suppress the anti-apoptotic protein BCL-2, resulting in an apoptosis-inducing action on cancer cells (21). Based on these results, the present study has been conducted to see how effective FPZ is at boosting cytotoxicity against colon cancer. The results of the combined use of FPZ and cisplatin to HCT116 cells demonstrated a beneficial partnership between the two drugs for producing cytotoxicity towards colon cancer cells *in vitro*.

A study published by Zong et al. in 2011, studied the chemosensitizer effect of different PTZ in different human lung cancer cells. The authors found that fluphenazine is able to increase the sensitivity of U1810 human non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) cells to the antineoplastic drug cisplatin, commonly used in the management of this type of cancer. These results were further supported by an increase in the expression of caspase-3 (indicative of apoptotic effect) after drug treatment of bleomycin-treated H23 cells, as well as an increase in chemotherapy-induced vacuolation (indicative of lysosomal dysfunction effect), on other cell lines (H23, H125, and U1752) (22).

On the other hand in Menilli study, The cytotoxic activity of fluphenazine (FPZ) in combination with UVA light was evaluated on three human tumor cell lines, HeLa, MSTO-211H and A431. The photobiological effect was determined following irradiation treatment in the presence of/after the removal of incubated FPZ. Under both conditions, FPZ proved to be very effective in killing tumor cells. Also results demonstrated that apoptosis was the main mechanism of cell death. Finally, an extremely high production of ROS was found, indicating a significant photodynamic mechanism involved in the photocytotoxic effect of FPZ. Taken together, their data show that FPZ following UVA irradiation behaves as an effective photoantiproliferative compound inducing apoptosis on various human tumor cells (23).

Goyette et al. (2019) showed that FLU affects proliferation, migration and invasion of MDA-MB-231 and Hs578T human breast cancer cells. The drug at a concentration of 20 μ M reduced invasion by about 75% and 40%, while the migration was reduced to less than 0.5 and 0.4 μ m/min, respectively for MDA-MB-231 and Hs578T cells. The analysis of the cell cycle showed cell cycle arrest in the G1/S phase in both cell lines: about 80% of MDA-

MB-231 cells and 70% of Hs578T cells were in the G1/S phase after FLU treatment (24).

The anticancer activity of FLU towards human breast cancer cells was also determined by Xu et al. (2019). The viability assay after FLU treatment was performed using different breast cancer cell lines. The anticancer effect of 24-hour FLU treatment was confirmed by a cell cycle regulation assay, which showed that in both cell lines (4T1 and MDAMB-231) the concentration of the drug at 20 μ M increased the G0/G1 phase distribution by about 9% compared with the control. Furthermore, the obtained data showed that FLU downregulated the expression levels of cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) 2, CDK4, cyclin D1 and cyclin E in a concentration-dependent manner as well as upregulating the expression of key controllers of the G1/S transition; p21 in both cell lines and p27 in MDA-MB-231 cells (25). The authors also confirmed the induction of apoptosis after FLU treatment, which showed that number of apoptotic cells increased from about 4% to 86% after 72-hour FLU treatment in the concentration range 0-20 μ M; and measurement of levels of caspase 3, Bax and Bcl-2, which showed increased cleavage of the caspase, decrease of Bcl-2 and a slight increase of Bax. The reactive oxygen species (ROS) level measured by the dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate assay dye confirmed that the 12-hour treatment with FLU increases the amount of ROS in both cell lines (25).

Therapeutic oncology's hallmark and objective for over three decades has been the creation of medicines that facilitate the effective clearance of cancer cells through apoptosis. As a result, apoptosis detection is a method for validating drug action in clinical trials. release of cytochrome c from the mitochondria into the cytoplasm is necessary for activating the intrinsic apoptotic pathway. Members of the BCL-2 family that promote apoptosis, such as BAX, cause the release of cytochrome c from the mitochondria, whereas members of the same family that suppress apoptosis, such as BCL-2, suppress it (13, 15, 25). In this research, apoptotic gene and protein expression of HCT116 cells treated with cisplatin alone and in combo with FPZ were assessed using western blot techniques as well as Real-time PCR. Our research showed that cisplatin monotherapy significantly increased the synthesis of pro-apoptotic BAX proteins, and cisplatin alongside FPZ further enhanced this effect. Moreover, when cisplatin and FPZ are used together, anti-apoptotic BCL-2 protein is downregulated more effectively than when cisplatin is used alone. We also discovered that cisplatin and FPZ work together to modulate bax and bcl-2 expression, implying a complicated molecular interaction between these two drugs.

This study is the very first one we have knowledge of that examines the effects of FPZ and its combination with cisplatin on CRC proliferation. Our result shows significant implications for the use of several medicines in cancer therapy. However, extra investigation is required to comprehend the underlying processes of the combinatorial strategy in colon cancer that improves efficacy while reducing damage to normal cells.

Figure 6: Fluphenazine and cisplatin caused cellular processes in HCT116 cells, depicted schematically. By reducing bcl-2 expression and boosting BAX expression, fluphenazine and cisplatin promote apoptosis.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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